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Design of a learning method based on Flipped-Classroom methodologies using SPOCs in an engineering course

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ABSTRACT

The actual development of communication and new technologies allows improving the pedagogy methodologies. In this work a new teaching methodology which combine online resources via Small Online Private Course (SPOC) with collaborative learning techniques is presented. This new methodology has been implemented in the course “Elasticity and Strength of Materials” in the Bachelor’s Degree in Industrial Technologies Engineering. As a benchmark of the methodology, 250 students and 6 teachers have been involved in the experience. The results of the study show how it is possible to improve the academic results with respect to the traditional teaching methodologies, improving as well transversal competences.

Conference Key Areas: Open and Online Engineering Education, Engineering Education Research, I want to contribute to solve local problems

Keywords: Learning design, Learning mark, Motivation, SPOC

INTRODUCTION

The technological development during the last decades, allows the teachers to employ new techniques based on online resources, adding value to the traditional teaching methodologies. Leading examples of this development are blended-learning (Bourne et al. 1996) and flipped-classroom (Kim et al. 2014). One of the main advances in these methodologies is the availability of moving part of the contents of the course to online resources, releasing time to apply other technologies in the classroom. The experiences during the last decades prove the improvements in engineering bachelors of collaborative learning, community learning and learning based on examples or projects (Smith et al. 2005).

Several studies show the improvements in the learning process of applying these new methodologies: Mendez and González (2011) balance the workload of each student based on its activity and its results using fuzzy logic techniques in a Control System course. The main conclusion of this work is the identification of the motivation as a

driven parameter for the academic success. In other words, the use of online learning methodologies not only eases the learning process but also increases the student motivation.

Yigit et al. (2013) proved that the mark results of the students in a coding subject are similar between traditional teaching and blended-learning methodologies. Using flipped-classroom in 3 different courses of engineering, humanities and social studies, Kim et al (2014) allowed identifying the main standards or principles for all courses.

Blaeper et al. (2014) studied the effect of the reduction of the on-site time in the classroom (2/3 of the total) for online contents in a physics course. Moreover the class was moved to an active learning classroom. The student's knowledges of the subject were improved with respect to the traditional method. At the same time, the perception of the students about the course has been upgraded. Proving the efficiency of the active learning classrooms, although the number of students in a collaborative classroom is lower than in a traditional classroom, the achievements are greater, reducing the total time of learning process.

One of the disadvantages of the online contents is its dependence to the spreading of the internet access in the country. Banday et al. (2014) studied this effect in developing countries where the internet access is lower than in the occidental ones, and proposed tools to reduce the effect of these disadvantages.

The emerging of new technologies allows the teacher to apply innovative techniques in the teaching process, making the study time become a game. Bodnar et al (2016) presented a review of the gamification of different courses in engineering proving that this technique increases the motivation and improves the learning process.

This work presents the implementation of a flipped-classroom methodology in the course "*Elasticity and Strength of Materials*" in the Bachelor Degree in Industrial Technologies Engineering during the course 2015/16 at the University Carlos III of Madrid. The theoretical sessions were moved to a Small Private Online Course (SPOC) and the time released was used for a collaborative learning technique. The results of the final exam show that the new methodology could improve the students' academic results and simplify the learning process.

1 TEACHING METHODOLOGY

The teaching methodology designed should fulfil the criteria of the European Higher Education Area (EHEA) applied in Spanish universities. Moreover, it should be done in the actual classrooms, timetable and groups of the Bachelor Degree in Industrial Technologies Engineering at the University Carlos III of Madrid

Each group of this engineering bachelor has 2 sessions of 2 hours per week, the first one (Aggregated group) with a maximum of 120 students and the second one is a reduced group of 40 students. Usually the Aggregated group is used to explain theoretical contents and the reduced sessions are employed to solve practical exercises. Subsequently the students should study the theory and then try to solve the problems by its own. The number of students per year is around 250, which are divided into 3 aggregated groups and 7 reduced groups.

The implemented methodology is based on the idea of flipped-class-room, because some of the common tasks done by the students in the classroom in the traditional methodology, are moved to homework and vice versa. The learning process is as can be seen in Figure 1:

Figure 1. Learning process implemented in the course

- Theory contents are recorded in videos and uploaded into the SPOC platform. These videos should be attended/viewed as homework before the class in the aggregate group. Therefore the students, instead of listening the teacher in the classroom, view the video and hence they can decide the time and rhythm of the explanation and even repeat selected parts. Moreover the contents are multiplatform accessible, so the students decide the way to access to the information
- The aggregate group sessions are used now for discussing the theory in a more active way, from the students' point of view. Moreover different problems are solved and discussed, moving the task done in the traditional methodology of the reduce group to the aggregate one. The bigger number of students enriches the discussion and the possible doubts of the theory.
- Finally, the reduced groups are re-designed to accomplish a collaborative learning process. The group of 40 students was divided in groups of 5. Each odd week the group of 5 should solve by its own a problem, discussing the doubts with the teacher. The even weeks the groups present and explain the solutions to the other students, each team member should present at least 1 time the solutions and answer the doubts of the other students and the teacher's questions.

2 EVALUATION STRATEGY

The traditional way of marking consists of 60 % the final exam mark (4 different problems) and the 40% of the course mark correspond to continuum assessment. This continuum assessment was composed by a 15% the laboratory marks and 25 % the partial exams. Moreover it is required at least 4.5/10 in the final exam to pass the course.

The new evaluation strategy conserves the old weight between the final exam and the continuum assessment but, in this case, the 25% corresponding to the partial exams were assigned to the marks corresponding to the teamwork evaluation: 1/3 of this mark corresponds to the solving evaluation of the team (equally for all the team members), 1/3 corresponds to the evaluation of the presentation, and the rest (1/3) is the mark of the answers to the teacher questions after the problem presentation.

3 SPOC ENROLMENT

Most students attend the SPOC course. The SPOC contents are videos, self-assessment exercises and evaluation problems. After each video, the students should answer a series of questions designed to test the understanding of the concepts explained in the video, these exercises or questions are not taken into account for the final assessment. The evaluation exams consist on 6 questions or problems at the end of each week. The entire course was divided in 13 weeks and the final mark is the

average of the marks of the 13 week's evaluation tests. Based on the results of these weekly tests, 83% of the students pass the SPOC course, 90 % of these obtain a mark bigger than 7/10 (mark grade B or A). Only 17% of the students did not pass the SPOC course, and 70% of this percentage gave up the SPOC course, hence they did not answer the tests. These results are considered positive, due to the fact that in all the courses there is a percentage of the students that give up the course without attending the final exam. This percentage (19%) was similar to the one of giving up the SPOC course.

4 RESULTS

The results of this work are compared with respect to the marks of the year 2014/15 and 2015/16 in the ordinary final exam of the course "*Elasticity and Strength of materials*". Besides the target population are different, the number of students involved is large enough to be considered as equally dispersed, 269 students in 2014/15 and 287 students in 2015/16. Moreover, the mean academic grading of both groups during the bachelor courses were similar. The mean academic grading of the student in 2014/15 was 6.19/10 and the grading of the students in 2015/16 was 6.05/10.

Table 1 shows the percentages of the total number of students that have passed the course, the percentage of students which pass the final exam, and the percentage of the students that have failed the exam (obtaining a mark greater than 4.5) but pass the course due to the continuum assessment mark. These results show that the percentage of the students who pass the course increase a 40% in relative terms, but the number of students with a mark greater than 5/10 in the final exam was increased in 78%. This means that a great number of students in 2014/15 did not pass the exam, but pass the course due to the continuum assessment mark.

	2014/15	2015/16	Differences
% Students pass course	47.21%	66.55%	41.0%
% Final exam positive	31.60%	56.45%	78.6%
% Students which pass the course due to the continuum, assessment.	15.61%	10.10%	-35.3%

Table 1. Percentage of students that pass the course in comparison with 2014/15

Table 2 shows the marks obtained by the students in the final exam for both 2014/15 and 2015/16 academic years. The number of students that give up the course decreased, which means that the number of students that considered that they were prepared for the exam increased. The percentage of students that did not pass the course decreased to a half in comparison with the previous year, and the percentage of passed increased. The more remarkable result is that only 3% of the students in 2014/15 obtained a B mark (7/10) and none of them an A mark (9/10). However, with the new methodology, 17% of the students obtained a B mark (7/10) and 6 % obtained an A mark (9/10). These results show that the knowledge acquired by the students can be considered remarkably better and it is translated into the marks of the students.

	2014/15	2015/16	Differences

Give up the course	23.79%	18.82%	-20.9%
Failed	44.61%	24.74%	-44.5%
Pass	28.62%	32.75%	14.4%
B mark	2.97%	17.07%	474.1%
A mark	0.00%	6.62%	
Total pass	31.60%	56.45%	78.6%

Table 1. Final exam marks distributions

Figure 2 depicts the distribution of the marks of the exam in the years 2014/15 and 2015/16, showing a normal distribution. In 2014/15 the normal distribution was centred in a mean value of 4.7 and a standard deviation of 1.39. Therefore the students did not pass the exam but passed the course due to the continuum assessment mark. The results due to the presented methodology, course 2015/16, shows a normal distribution centred in 5.89 with a standard deviation of 1.84. Most of the students passed the exam, and the number of marks higher than B increased.

Fig. 1. Final exam mark distribution 2014/15 and 2015/16.

5 LEVEL OF COURSE SATISFACTION

The students from the University Carlos III of Madrid answer a satisfaction poll about the teaching methodology for every course and year. This poll has been used to evaluate the presented teaching methodology. It is important to remark that the students answer the poll before the final exam, so the answers are independent of the increased mean mark in the final exam. The course has 6 teachers in 3 aggregated groups and 7 reduced groups. Only 1 teacher was different between the 2014/15 and 2015/16 courses; that change affected only to the 30% of the students. The mean results of satisfaction of the students in 2014/15 was 3.51/5 whereas in 2015/16 was 3.6/5. There is a slightly rise in the satisfaction, but not significant to be considered. The significant change in the poll results was in the poll's comments. In 2014/15 the students' comments or complaints were in the way of:

- The students considered that the number of problems were scarce

- The course syllabus is huge and each division is taught summarily
- The theory sessions are difficult
- The theory sessions are useless

In 2015/16 the comments or complaints of the students, can be classified also in:

- The students required more theory concepts in the on-site sessions
- There are weeks with partial exams of other subject that reduced the available time for the SPOC
- The students requested partial exams
- The presentations of the other students, explaining the problem resolutions are useless

The similar values of satisfaction in both years conclude that the new methodology has been similarly accepted by the students. Moreover there are different student profiles and some has better acceptance under new methodologies. In the traditional methodology, there is a group of students requesting more exercises, with the new methodology a new group appear requiring more theory weight in the on-site sessions, similar to the traditional method. The new method forces the student to learn out of his comfort zone, they are used to a passive learning in which listening to the teacher is the main task. In the new methodology they should study and prepare the subject by their own. The new method pushes the student to collaborate in team works and explain his results to the group by a public appearance, which usually turns out in complaints.

6 CONCLUSIONS

It can be considered the success of the new method, due to its results in comparison with the traditional methodology. Although a deeper analysis, including more polls and a bigger population is required to identify the aspects that causes the success, even so it can be identify possible success parameters of this experience:

- The blank sheet of paper magic: the most important time in the learning process is the one in which the students try to solve a problem by their own. Although the method assures that the teacher joins the students in this experience and serves as guidance.
- The relationship student-professor. The methodology implies a closer relation, which confers more confidence and reduces the expert syndrome in the teacher understanding the student point of view. This experience not only improves the learning process, but also gives to the teacher the opportunity of enhancing his explanations in the weaker knowledges points of the students.
- The spreading of enthusiasm. The effort and passion of the teacher is spread or transmitted to the students, and his answers to the teachers are an “extra” effort, trying to keep up with the professors.
- The task of every week homework. The demanding task of SPOC videos prevents to quit the course and enable a better understanding of every lesson. The success of the results is due to the fact that the students have worked more and better, because a better guidance in the learning process.
- The student behaviour depends on the environment. The traditional method used during decades, teaching by a passive listening, does not prepare the students for the professional career, where should be active and collaborative. This new methodology gives the principal role of the learning to the students.

- The new methodology is not only a success in the subject taught, but also increases transversal knowledges e.g. “the capacity to communicate its knowledge in public appearance” and “team working”

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